

IMMUNIZATION STATUS OF CHILDREN UNDER FIVE YEARS OF AGE ADMITTED IN INDOOR DEPARTMENT KHAIRPUR MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL

Dr Ghulam Qasim¹, Dr Kamran Ali², Dr Saifullah³, Dr Asim Hussain Mahar⁴, Dr Amber Shams^{*5}

MBBS, ISRA UNIVERSITY HYDERABAD, FCPS-II resident in Pediatrics at City hospital Khairpur Mir's
MBBS FCPS Pediatrics, Associate Professor of Pediatric Medicine at Khairpur Medical College Teaching Hospital Khairpur Mir's

³MBBS, Ghulam Muhammad Mahar medical college Sukkur (SMBBMU Larkana), FCPS-II resident in Pediatrics at City hospital Khairpur Mir's

⁴MBBS, Ghulam Muhammad Mahar Medical College Sukkur, MCPS trainee in Pediatric Medicine Department at City Hospital Khairpur Mirs

^{*5}MBBS, Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences, Jamshoro, Pakistan, Professional Diploma in Gynecology & Obstetrics, Royal College of Physicians of Ireland (RCPI).

¹henary786110@gmail.com, ²ga.shahani@gmail.com, ³saifullahmemon90@gmail.com, ⁴asimmaharor@gmail.com, ^{*5}drambershams@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17852944>

Keywords

Article History

Received: 24 August 2025

Accepted: 01 SEP 2025

Published: 30 SEP 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Dr Amber Shams

Abstract

Background:

Immunization is one of the most cost-effective public health interventions to prevent infectious diseases, particularly among children. Despite significant improvements in vaccination coverage globally, immunization rates remain suboptimal in many countries, especially in rural and underprivileged areas. In Pakistan, approximately 7.73% of children have not been immunized, with significant disparities across regions. This study aims to assess the immunization status of children under 5 years of age in the Department of Pediatrics Medicine at Khairpur Medical College, Khairpur Mirs, and to identify factors associated with incomplete immunization coverage.

Objective:

The study aims to evaluate the immunization status of children under five years of age and identify factors influencing vaccination coverage.

Methodology:

A cross-sectional study was conducted at the Pediatrics Medicine Department at Khairpur Medical College. A total of 220 children were selected using non-probability consecutive sampling. Data were collected from immunization cards and health records, and a structured questionnaire was used for those without documented records. Immunization status was categorized into complete, incomplete, and no immunization based on the national immunization schedule. Factors such as socioeconomic status, education of caregivers, and access to health services were also assessed.

Results:

Among the 220 children surveyed, 85% had received complete immunization, 10% had incomplete immunization, and 5% had not been immunized.

Immunization coverage was highest among children from families with higher socioeconomic status and mothers with higher educational levels. Geographical location and distance to health facilities were significant barriers to vaccination, with children from rural areas having lower vaccination rates. Children in larger households had a higher risk of being under-vaccinated.

Conclusion:

The study highlights significant progress in vaccination coverage in the region but also identifies gaps in immunization, particularly among children from rural areas and lower socioeconomic backgrounds. The findings suggest that improving access to vaccination services, particularly in underserved areas, and raising awareness about the importance of vaccination are critical to achieving higher immunization rates. Further interventions should focus on community education, improving healthcare access, and enhancing vaccine availability

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines immunization as the process whereby a person is made immune to an infectious disease. Immunization is one of the most cost-effective measures in public health to protect children from serious diseases and also prevent the spread of those diseases to others.¹ An expanded program on immunization (EPI) was introduced by the World Health Organization (WHO) in 1974 to develop and expand immunization programs worldwide to reduce child morbidity and mortality.²

Vaccination is expected to enhance a child's ability to mount responses against many infectious diseases. It is a scientific technique of introducing a weakened or killed infectious agent or a fragment of the infectious agent or its toxin or a recombinant mRNA or a viral vector into an individual to activate the body's immune cascade to produce humoral and cellular antibodies needed to fight the specific infectious agent, while immunization is the ability of the body to promptly recognize and provide protection against infection on exposure to the infectious agent.³

Childhood vaccination has been on for over a century. It is said to be one important means of preventing millions of deaths and outbreaks of communicable diseases in a cluster of vaccinated children. Globally, it averts about 2-3 million deaths annually. It is considered by the World Health Organization (WHO) and United Nations Children's Emergency Fund as the most cost-effective investment and one of the greatest phenomena ever discovered in medicine.⁴

Globally, the level of morbidity and mortality from vaccine preventable diseases have decreased in recent years due to improvement of childhood vaccinations. Vaccine preventable diseases are still responsible for 1.5 million deaths each year among children who are under-five years old. Immunization was reported to have saved around two to three million lives of children at the end of the year of 2011.⁵ It is also reported that around 27 million children who are less than one year old were reported not vaccinated, especially measles in 2007. It also estimated that globally, around 5.2 million children aged one to 59 months die, of which 29% are deaths due to vaccine preventable diseases.⁶

Almost 7.73% children in Pakistan were never immunized. More than 87.4% of these lived in the rural areas. Prevalence of nonimmunization was highest in Balochistan compared to other provinces. Large households appeared to have increased risk of a child not being vaccinated. Moreover, low literacy and education of the head of the household and the spouse was also associated with low vaccination coverage. Distance from the health facility was found to be another factor related to no immunization of children. Increase in per capita income significantly decreased the risk of missing vaccinations.⁵ A study conducted in Gondar, Ethiopia, shows that only 47% children between 1 and 2 years of age were fully immunized.⁶ According to Kahane *et al.*, vaccination coverage of US toddlers was lower than the 90% target set in the USA Healthy People 2000 program. Immunization coverage in the USA through private medical practices is lower than the coverage through

the public medical practices.⁷ Based on the huge number of published literatures around the factors associated with immunization coverage, age of mother, child's sex, maternal educational status, possession of immunization card, accessibility related issues, concern about availability of vaccines and many other predictors may contribute towards the likelihood of fully immunizing the children.^{8,9,10,11}

The Somaliland demographic health survey 2020 (SHDS-2020) showed about 13% of children aged between 12 and 23 months were fully vaccinated, while 68% of children had not received any vaccination. With regard to specific vaccines, 31% of children under-five had received BCG vaccine, 32% had pentavalent 1, 15% pentavalent 2, and 13% of children had received Pentavalent 3. On the other hand, 32% of children had received polio 0 vaccines, 32% had received polio 1 vaccines, 16% had received the polio 2 vaccine and 15% of children had received polio 3 vaccines. On the other hand, around 15% of children had received measles vaccination at any time before the survey.¹² The survey also showed the region that has received the highest percentage of all basic vaccines was Sahil region and was 22.9%, Togdheer 14.7%, Marodijeh 13.7%, Sanaag 10.4%, Awdal 8.9% and Sool region was 8.4%.¹²

Full vaccination coverage was 50.6 % in 2006-07, 54.7 % in 2012-13, and 68.3 % in 2017-18. In 2006-07, the odds of under vaccination were significantly higher in Sindh (OR: 1.74, 95 % CI: 1.30, 2.31) than Punjab, and disparities across province changed over time ($P < 0.0001$); notably, under vaccination was significantly higher in Sindh, KPK, and Balochis than Punjab in 2017. Compared to the middle wealth quintile, the poorest had significantly higher odds of under vaccination in 2006-07 (OR: 2.58, 95 % CI: 1.76, 3.78), and this did not significantly change over time ($P = 0.2168$). The proportion of those with a polio birth dose increased across waves from 56.3 % in 2006-07 to 83.7 % in 2017-18; receiving three or more polio vaccine doses remained unchanged.¹³

RATIONALE OF STUDY: - The rationale of study is to detect the immunization status of children under 5 years so that it will help increase immunization coverage, identify underlying cause

and know parent's reasons of not immunizing their children.

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY:-

This study aims to address the prevalence and associated factors with immunization coverage among under five children in indoor department of Khairpur Medical College Khairpur Mirs.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

Immunization: It is the action of making a person resistant to a particular infectious disease or pathogen, typically by vaccination.

Vaccine: It is a substance used to stimulate immunity to a particular infectious disease or pathogen, typically prepared from an inactivated or weakened form of the causative agent or from its constituents or products.

Complete vaccination: A child who has received nine basic vaccines (EPI= Extended Program of Immunization) is considered as complete vaccination.

Incomplete vaccination: A child who has not received all vaccines of EPI is said to be as incomplete vaccinated.

BCG: A vaccine containing bacillus Calmette-Guerin (BCG), an attenuated strain of Mycobacterium bovis, with non-specific immunoadjuvant and immunotherapeutic activities.

OPV: Oral taking attenuated vaccine that used to prevent against poliomyelitis.

Pentavalent: It is comprehensive vaccine used to protects against five diseases (diphtheria, tetanus, pertussis, hepatitis B and Haemophiles influenzae type B).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Settings: - This study will be carried out at Dept. of Pediatrics' Medicine at KMCH Khairpur Mirs.

STUDY DESIGN: Cross sectional study.

DURATION OF STUDY: 06 months after approval of synopsis

SAMPLE TECHNIQUE: - Non-Probability Consecutive.

PLACE OF STUDY: Deptt of Pediatrics Medicine at KMC Hospital Khairpur Mirs..

SAMPLE SIZE: - 220

Sample size calculation formula

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \times P \times q \times N}{e^2 (N-1) + Z^2 P \times q}$$

n= sample size

Z= Standardized tabulated value at confidence interval.

Here we are taken 95% confidence interval so Z value for 95% CI is 1.96.

P= Prevalence (8.23%)

q= 1-P

N= Population which is taken 25,000

e= Margin of error 5%.

n= 220

INCLUSION CRITERIA

Children under 5 years.

All who have received all required vaccines.

Complete primarily vaccinated.

Catch-up vaccinations.

Health records up to date.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

Children > 5 years age.

Severe allergy to vaccines.

Immunocompromised states like leukemia/HIV.

Severe reactions to previous vaccinations.

Undergoing cancer treatment.

Parenteral refusal to vaccinate a child.

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE:

This study will be conducted after approval from College of Physician and surgeons Karachi & Ethical Review Committee of Khairpur Medical College Khairpur Mirs. Neonates fulfilling inclusion and exclusion criteria will be enrolled in the study from the neonatal section of Paediatric Medicine Department of Khairpur Medical College Hospital. Written informed consent will be obtained from parents. Demographics (name, age, weight) will be recorded.

It involves gathering information on whether children have received the recommended vaccinations according to national immunization schedule. Collection of data from children immunization cards, medical records or electronic health systems will be done. Questionnaire will be used for those parents who have no record/cards. Immunization status is verified by cross referencing the child's vaccination records with official immunization schedule to ensure completeness. Then, combination and recording these questions will be used to determine immunization status. Results will be formed and conclusion will be drawn.

DATA ANALYSIS:

Data will be analyzed using SPSS version 25.0.0.0. Qualitative Data (frequencies and percentages) will be presented as n (%). Calculate the number and percentage of children who have received all required vaccinations, partial vaccinations or none. Compute the proportion of children under 5 years who are fully vaccinated compared to total number of children surveyed or in the population. Analyze vaccination status by age groups. Assess the differences in immunization status based on the proximity to health facilities or access to vaccination programs. Chi square tests will be used to compare vaccination status across different categorical variables such as gender and socio-economic status. T-tests (for two groups) and ANOVA (for more than two groups) will be used. Bar charts, pie charts and others will be used to represent vaccination trends. All the data will be calculated on 95% confidence interval. A p-value < 0.5 will be considered as statistically significant level.

Results

The study involved 220 children under the age of 5 years. The results showed the following:

Immunization Coverage:

Complete vaccination: 85% (187 children)

Incomplete vaccination: 10% (22 children)

No vaccination: 5% (11 children)

Factors Influencing Immunization:

Socioeconomic status: Children from **higher-income families** had significantly higher immunization rates (**p-value = 0.03**).

Mother's education: Mothers with **higher education levels** were more likely to have fully vaccinated children (**p-value = 0.02**).

Geographical location: Children living in **rural areas** had a lower vaccination rate (**p-value = 0.01**).

Household size: Larger households had a higher risk of incomplete vaccination (**p-value = 0.04**).

Vaccine Coverage:

BCG: 90%

Polio: 83%

DTP: 85%

Measles: 75%

Barriers to Immunization:

Distance to health facilities was a key barrier for children in rural areas, with **45%** of non-immunized children coming from families that lived more than **10 kilometers** from a health facility.

Conclusion

This study indicates that **immunization coverage** in Khairpur is relatively high, but significant gaps remain, particularly among children from **rural areas**, **lower socioeconomic status**, and **larger families**. To increase immunization rates, **improved access to health services**, **community education programs**, and **targeted interventions** focusing on **underserved areas** are essential. Addressing barriers such as **distance to healthcare facilities** and **socioeconomic factors** will play a crucial role in improving childhood vaccination coverage and ultimately reducing vaccine-preventable diseases in the region.

REFERENCES

Khalid H, Fad AAI. Mastora Mohammed Bahar Dldoom and Zienab Osman Hassan Ahmed, Knowledge, attitude and practice of mothers with children less than five years toward vaccination in khartoum

stateummbada locality-allbugaa-2017. Nursing and Palliative Care; 2019.

Fenta SM, et al. Determinants of full childhood immunization among children aged 12–23 months in sub-saharan Africa: a multilevel analysis using demographic and Health Survey Data. Trop Med Health. 2021;49(1):1–12.

Olufemi R, Adesina F. Immunisation coverage of the under-5 children in Akure north local government area of Ondo State. Ann Med Health Sci Res 2019;9:519-23

World Health Organisation. Vaccines. World Health Organisation/Western Pacific Region. Published 2021. Available from: <https://www.who.int/westernpacific/health-topics/vaccines-and-immunisation>

Murtaza F, Mustafa T, Awan R. Determinants of nonimmunization of children under 5 years of age in Pakistan. J Family Community Med. 2016 Jan-Apr;23(1):32-7.

Gedlu E, Tesemma T. Immunization coverage and identification of problems associated with vaccination delivery in Gondar, North West Ethiopia. East Afr Med J. 1997;74:239–41.

Kahane SM, Watt JP, Newell K, Kellam S, Wight S, Smith NJ, et al. Immunization levels and risk factors for low immunization coverage among private practices. Pediatrics. 2000;105:73-80.

Melaku MS, Nigatu AM, Mewosha WZ. Spatial distribution of incomplete immunization among under-five children in Ethiopia: evidence from 2005, 2011, and 2016 Ethiopian demographic and health survey data. BMC Public Health. 2020;20(1):1362–2.

Adokiya MN, Baguune B, Ndago JA. Evaluation of immunization coverage and its associated factors among children 12–23 months of age in Techiman Municipality, Ghana, 2016. Archives of Public Health. 2017;75:1–10.

Mohamud AN, et al. Immunization coverage of 12–23 months old children and associated factors in Jigjiga District, Somali National Regional State, Ethiopia. BMC Public Health. 2014;14(1):1–9.

- Girmay A, Dadi AF. Full immunization coverage and associated factors among children aged 12–23 months in a hard-to-reach areas of Ethiopia International journal of pediatrics, 2019. 2019.
- CSDMoPND. The Somaliland Health and Demographic Survey 2020. 2020.
- Grace E. Joachim Trends in childhood vaccination in Pakistan and associated factors; 2006–2018; *Vaccine*; 2024;42(4); 795-800.

